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**TRANSATLANTIC PARTNERSHIP IN
CHECK?
THE NORTH ATLANTIC TREATY
ORGANISATION (NATO) IN THE MIDST
OF THE UNITED STATES AND RUSSIA.**

Carolina Ambinder

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Policy Statement

On 6 March 2025, the Secretary General of the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO), Mark Rutte, said: 'the transatlantic partnership remains the bedrock of our Alliance' (NATO, 2025). This statement refers to the current uncertain relationship between NATO's European member countries[1] and the United States (US) due to current US President Donald Trump's direction to reduce spending on the organization. This orientation has continued even after the recently completed three years of the War in Ukraine (2022 - present), during which Trump has sought a resolution with the presidents of Russia, Vladimir Putin, and Ukraine, Volodymyr Zelensky, disregarding Europe's direct participation in the negotiations. Additionally, at the beginning of his second term (January 2025 - present), Trump indicated geopolitical ambitions in the Arctic Circle, aimed at Greenland, which is also a NATO member (as an autonomous territory of Denmark). This policy brief analyses NATO's position in current international politics, with an emphasis on relations with the US and Russia.

Background

War in Ukraine (2022 - current)

On 24 February 2025, the Russia vs. Ukraine War marked its third anniversary. During this period, specifically until 4 March 2025, the United States Department of Defense (U.S DoD) reported that US\$ 66.5 billion was spent on the conflict (DoD, 2025). European countries contributed US\$ 69 billion in war aid, primarily from North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO) nations. However, on March 3, 2025, the White House announced a pause in military assistance to Ukraine (Beale, 2025). Likewise, as of today, in NATO, the US covers 64% of the costs, while Europe accounts for the remaining 36% (Beale, 2025); in this context, the Trump II administration plans to reduce US involvement in the organization's maintenance.

However, this is not the only current initiative that has the practical effect of distancing the US from Europe, particularly NATO countries. Regarding the attempt at a ceasefire between Russia and Ukraine, which Trump spearheaded as one of his campaign promises, the US president has been engaged in trilateral dialogue with Russian President Vladimir Putin and Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky.

On February 28, 2025, however, at a meeting between Trump and Zelensky, Trump raised the tone concerning the need for Ukraine to accept the US proposal. The economic highlight is the exploitation of rare earth minerals in exchange for a guarantee of military support after the ceasefire. The effort to align US interests has also been realized in the Arctic Circle, particularly concerning Greenland.

Arctic Circle: Greenland

'The next few years will be promising in that they will allow us to see whether or not the ecological imperatives - present in the care taken to safeguard the polar ecosystems as humanity's 'untouchable' heritage - will tend to give way in the face of the 'temptation' to exploit their precious resources' (Duarte, 2015, p. 458). After a decade, the ambition to exploit polar ecosystems, as observed by Duarte (2015), peaked.

In particular, climate issues have caused the Arctic Circle to thaw, favoring shorter seasonal sea transit between East and West (Duarte, 2015, p. 258) and increasing the efficiency of international trade. The region also presents the possibility of exploring new sources of oil and gas and engaging in fishing activities, enhancing its strategic importance.

Despite the Arctic Council's existence, comprised of Russia, Norway, Iceland, the United States, Canada[2], Finland, Sweden, and Denmark (with representation from its autonomous region of Greenland) for almost thirty years, practical cooperation and governance in the Arctic remain somewhat ambiguous. This is largely due to the complexity of the post-Cold War context and the securitization of various issues. Nevertheless, Russia emerges as the primary actor in this arena, owing to its status as the nation with the largest fleet of icebreakers globally and the only nuclear icebreaker fleet of its kind (Pereira, De Oliveira, Martins and Campos, 2024, p. 153). This provides quantitative and qualitative advantages for enhanced and effective actions in the region.

From this geopolitical perspective of the interaction between spatial delimitation and power relations, Donald Trump addressed the US Congress on March 4, 2025. In his speech, he included the ambition to 'take Greenland one way or another' (BBC News Brasil, 2025). This statement is expansionist in nature and considers the geographical proximity of the autonomous region of Denmark to the North American subcontinent and important iron ore deposits (Duarte, 2015, p. 460), reflecting the greater US

attention to the issue since the launch of its new Arctic Strategy in 2024 (Wiltgen, 2024).

Findings

The pause in U.S. aid to Ukraine and the reduction in the hegemonic power's spending on NATO raise questions about the historic partnership between Europe and the United States, solidified since the end of the Second World War in 1945. The creation of NATO directly resulted from this situation, institutionalizing international defense cooperation through the aforementioned collective security pact in 1949 [3].

On the one hand, the trilateral dynamic (USA, Russia, and Ukraine) of negotiating the Russia-Ukraine War alters the world order that has been in place for eight decades, excluding Europe, particularly NATO, from the primary decisions on international security. On the other hand, it revives the dynamics of the Cold War (1945 - 1991), with the USA and Russia (formerly the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics - USSR) playing a leading role in the system.

Finally, the Arctic is a concern for the relationship between the US and NATO and the US and Russia. By taking a verbally incisive stance on Greenland, Trump has created diplomatic animosity with fellow NATO member Denmark, whose practical response has been to announce increased military security in the autonomous region (JP News, 2025) and the victory of the center-right party in the elections of 11th March 2025. In its desire to further project into the Arctic, the US encounters the central actor in this Polar Circle: Russia.

Recommendations

Regarding the relationship between the US and NATO, first, on 6 March 2025, the Secretary General of the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO), Mark Rutte, said: 'the transatlantic partnership remains the bedrock of our Alliance' (NATO, 2025). In other words, the relationship between these actors is expected to remain deep and free of tensions, primarily for greater security concerning the functioning and existence of the largest military alliance on the planet.

However, this does not exclude the need for Europe, particularly NATO member countries, to increase their military spending, reduce their dependence on the US, and enhance their deterrent effect on Russia through a balance of power[4]. Currently, only 23 of the 32 member countries of the organization meet the target of spending 2% of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on defense (Madslien, 2025), most notably Poland, which reached 4.7% of its GDP on defense spending in the context of the war in Ukraine.

The relationship between the US and Russia must recognize the importance of diplomacy. On the part of the US, this must include valuing democracies such as Ukraine and other European countries, in line with the premises of US foreign policy. As the superpowers responsible for the world's largest nuclear arsenal, the US and Russia's instability could threaten international security in a way not seen since the Cuban Missile Crisis (1962), the peak of Cold War tensions.

One area of focus is the desire for greater U.S. action in the Arctic, which necessitates an increase in the country's military capacity in the region; in other words, it requires not only the possession of resources but also the ability to operationalize them, including joint exercises and multidomain simulations featuring land, air, and naval components.

Final Considerations

The reduction in US financial participation in NATO raises questions about the organization's format and continuity, as it favors not only the acquisition of military means but also research in the sector, promoting Science, Technology, and Innovation (ST&I) for its future. However, once NATO's European member countries become aware of the need to increase defense spending (some of them to at least reach the 2% of GDP recommended by NATO), this reduction in US participation can be offset.

This compensation is also possible in the form of financial aid to Ukraine in its war against Russia, which the US has announced it is pausing. Russia has increased its military spending exponentially, keeping the Western community on high alert regarding international security. Concerning the Russia-Ukraine war, it is evident that behind the attempts to negotiate within a trilateral framework centrally managed by the US lies the future of the relationship between these superpowers and the long-term configuration of international politics.

Finally, it should be remembered that while the Arctic Circle refers to the multidimensional political, economic, and military power struggle between the US and Russia, it also serves as a stage for maintaining relations between the world's leading power and NATO. After all, the region includes several members of this organization, such as Canada, Denmark in the form of Greenland, Iceland, Finland, and Sweden - the latter two joining in 2023 and 2024, respectively, due to the regional and potentially global instability stemming from the Russia-Ukraine war. The transatlantic partnership between Europe and the US faces obstacles, particularly from NATO, and its stabilization will be decisive in shaping the relationship between the US and Russia, central players in international politics.[5]

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[1] NATO member countries can be found at: https://www.nato.int/nato-welcome/index_pt.html

[2] A sovereign state about which Trump has also made expansionist comments this term, stating, 'I would love to see Canada become the 51st state' of the US (Tortella, 2025).

[3] NATO is the military alliance of the West, and Article 5 of its Charter states that an attack on one member country will be considered an attack on all, requiring a collective response.

[4] In this case, the concept of 'balance of power' refers to the dynamics of mutual armament between certain actors, whereby the power of one balances that of another, dissuading (discouraging) specific conflictive action

[5] This policy brief has not set out to analyze China's role in this situation. Still, it does note the importance of following the alliance that has been strengthened between China, Russia, and North Korea as a result of Russia vs. Ukraine war, in a trilateral partnership that has never been seen in history and which has economic, military (nuclear) and population weight.

Carolina Ambinder (ECEMAR; UniLaSalle-RJ; InterAgency Institute): Carolina Ambinder has a Ph.D in Strategic Defense and Security Studies (Universidade Federal Fluminense). She is Head of Policy and Strategy at the Air Force Command and Staff School (ECEMAR), Professor of International Relations at UniLaSalle-RJ, and Global Security Researcher at the InterAgency Institute (IA).

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7503-3809>

InterAgency Institute

<https://interagency.institute/>
contact@interagency.institute

Editor-in-chief: Larlecianne Piccolli

